

CoAct
Database

Ten Years of Global Climate Action

Insights from the CoAct Database

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NOVEMBER 2025

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10 November 2025

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Date 10 November 2025

Suggested citation Chan, S., Glass, L.-M., Hagenström, P., Imbach, P., Peterson, L., Reyes de la Lanza, S., & Van den Wall Bake, K. (2025). *Ten years of global climate action – Insights from the CoAct Database*. Radboud University; German Institute of Development and Sustainability (IDOS); Tropical Agricultural Research and Higher Education Center (CATIE).

Acknowledgements We would like to extend thanks to all those who contributed to this work: Tea Skrinjaric, Cécilia Beauvais, Daniela André Campos, Fermin Blanco Zahid, Gustavo Poveda Won, Marcella Claudette Sarti Arellano, and Mariaclara López Ruiz (CATIE), Dinorah León González (IDOS), and Helena Kauer, Isa Cremers, and Rhiannon Jacob-Goldak (Radboud University), as well as to our collaborators in previous CoAct/C-CID iterations: Andrew Deneault, Gianmarco Diprima (IDOS), Thomas Hale (University of Oxford), Robert Falkner (London School of Economics and Political Science), and Harro van Asselt (University of Cambridge).

This analysis was developed jointly by the ACHIEVE, BioCAM4, and CAMDA projects. The ACHIEVE project is funded by the European Union's *Horizon Europe* Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No. 101137625. The BioCAM4 project is supported through the Government of Canada's *New Frontiers in Research Fund (NFRF)* (Grant No. NFRFI-2023-00225), the *German Research Foundation (DFG)*, and *UKRI's Economic and Social Research Council (ESRC)* (Grant No. ES/Z000092/1). The CAMDA project is funded by the *IKEA Foundation* (Grant No. G-2306-02289). The views and opinions expressed are those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union, the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA), or any other funders. Neither the European Union nor the granting authorities can be held responsible for them.

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The ACHIEVE project has received funding from the European Union's HORIZON EUROPE Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement No 101137625.

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Executive Summary

Over the past decade, cooperative climate action has become a central feature of global climate governance. Thousands of businesses, subnational governments, civil society organizations, and international partnerships have mobilized to complement and support multilateral and state-led efforts. Using insights from the CoAct Database (formerly N-CID), and data from a sample of 387 initiatives, this chapter takes stock of developments since 2013 and looks ahead to how cooperative action can contribute to the implementation of the Paris Agreement, particularly addressing priorities arising from the Global Stocktake (GST). Our analysis yields five headline findings.

1. Rapid expansion, but uneven focus. CCIIs have multiplied since 2015 and increasingly address adaptation, yet mitigation continues to dominate. While themes such as energy, land use, and industry remain strong, adaptation-related themes, e.g., particularly water, oceans, and resilience, remain underrepresented.

2. Effectiveness is improving, but equity gaps persist.

Many CCIIs now deliver more tangible outputs and report more systematically, yet overall output effectiveness has plateaued since 2018. Smaller and less-resourced initiatives often lag behind due to capacity constraints, while limited accountability mechanisms—such as monitoring, transparent governance, and membership control—continue to hinder performance.

3. Participation has broadened, but inclusivity remains limited. Participation of actors in CCIIs has expanded, but leadership and decision-making remain concentrated among Northern and institutional actors. Indigenous Peoples and Local Communities (IPLCs) are largely absent from governance structures, while engagement of businesses, investors, and local civil society has stagnated in recent years.

4. Stronger alignment with global priorities is needed. Future orchestration should strengthen coherence between CCIIs and priorities in the implementation of the Paris Agreement, for instance those emerging from the Global Stocktake (GST). Integrating adaptation, nature, and resilience more effectively—and fostering synergies across thematic axes such as energy–nature, food–energy, and cities–ecosystems—can enhance the systemic impact of cooperative climate action.

5. The next five years are critical. To sustain momentum and credibility, CCIIs and orchestrators, such as the High-Level Climate Champions, COP presidencies and the UNFCCC secretariat, must focus on inclusion, capacity, and accountability—especially in underrepresented regions. Expanding implementation and participation in low- and middle-income countries will improve both effectiveness and procedural justice. Deliberate orchestration by COP Presidencies, policymakers, and leading CCIIs can ensure that cooperative climate action evolves toward greater balance, legitimacy, and transformative impact.

While cooperative climate action has expanded and matured over the past decade, its transformative potential remains only partly realized, calling for deeper structural and systemic change. As the world moves on to implement the Paris Agreement, cooperative initiatives should help accelerate ambition, bridge gaps in implementation, and foster more equitable and effective global climate action.

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1. Introduction

Over the past decade, cooperative climate action has become a defining feature of the global response to climate change. Beyond intergovernmental negotiations, the multilateral climate regime has increasingly sought to orchestrate voluntary action by subnational governments, such as cities and regions, as well as private businesses, financial institutions, and civil society organizations, among other non-state actors. This turn toward cooperation was catalysed in the run-up to the 21st Conference of the Parties (COP21) in Paris, when the *Lima–Paris Action Agenda* mobilized a growing constellation of cooperative initiatives, setting the stage for the *Marrakech Partnership for Global Climate Action* and the recognition of both individual and cooperative voluntary efforts through the *Non-State Actor Zone for Climate Action (NAZCA)* platform, also known as the *Global Climate Action Portal (GCAP)*. These efforts institutionalized a new interface between the United Nations Framework Convention for Climate Change (UNFCCC) process and non-Party stakeholders, giving rise to what became known as the *Global Climate Action Agenda (GCAA)*.

Over time, the GCAA has consolidated its efforts through the leadership of the *High-Level Climate Champions* and a range of flagship campaigns, including the *Race to Zero*, the *Race to Resilience*, and the *Breakthrough Agenda*. Together, these platforms have sought to mobilise non-Party stakeholders to commit to more ambitious climate action and contribute to shared goals for mitigation, adaptation, and systemic transformation. However, the scope of cooperative climate action goes above and beyond activities under the GCAA. There is an ever-growing groundswell of efforts encompassing diverse multistakeholder partnerships, networks, and alliances. These bring together non-state and subnational actors and seek to catalyse more ambitious target setting, planning, implementation, and progress tracking. Examples of such initiatives include city networks like ICLEI and C40, and corporate initiatives like the Science-Based Targets Initiative (SBTi) or RE100. Importantly, the post-Paris governance landscape has seen a steady growth of initiatives that take climate action through cooperative arrangements, many of them being launched at annual COPs and other high-level events.

This report focuses on analysing the landscape of cooperative initiatives that have been active since 2013. We understand such initiatives as multi-stakeholder arrangements that mobilize and coordinate voluntary commitments or joint actions toward climate objectives. The purpose of the analysis is two-fold: (1) to provide an assessment of the growth, performance, participation, and implementation patterns of such initiatives, and (2) to map their activities against priorities that emerged from the first Global Stocktake (GST), identified as thematic ‘axes’ and ‘objectives’ by the Brazilian COP30 presidency (Aranha Correa do Lago, 2025). This analysis responds to ongoing calls both within and outside the United Nations (UN) system to enhance the credibility of voluntary pledges by non-Party Stakeholders, address greenwashing concerns, boost accountability, and contribute to global stocktaking efforts through more transparent reporting and tracking of ambition and implementation. The results provide a systematic mapping of the evolution of initiatives and assess emerging integrity concerns in terms of effectiveness, inclusiveness, equity, and justice considerations, among other dimensions. Moreover, the recommendations can inform current and future COP Presidencies and governments regarding how to better orchestrate, and engage with, initiatives.

Methodology

The CoAct Database (formerly: Climate-Cooperative Initiatives Database; Chan et al., 2025) tracks cooperative climate action and provides insights into the landscape of Cooperative Climate Initiatives (CCIs) over the last decade. The database tracks over 100 different variables, including output performance indicators, actor roles and compositions, and accountability and transparency mechanisms. The majority of CCIs in CoAct have been launched at COPs and other UN climate summits since 2014. In the current mapping, we include a subsample of 360 CCIs that meet the following criteria: (1) the initiative addresses climate change adaptation and/or mitigation; (2) the initiative includes 2 or more actors; (3) the initiative includes at least one (non-Party) non-state or subnational actor; and (4) the initiative works across borders. We included an additional 27 initiatives that are either listed on NAZCA or launched during recent COPs to ensure full coverage of UNFCCC-recognized initiatives. Moreover, initiatives specifically focused on nature-based climate action play an important role in our sample.

CoAct data is collected from publicly available sources, such as websites, social media posts, reports, or news articles. The sourced data is coded according to a standardized codebook by trained coders, with most CCIs undergoing multiple annual or biannual coding cycles to ensure intercoder reliability. However, the dataset is preliminary, and the next steps include formal validation and blind double-coding checks. Moreover, we use the most recent data available for each CCI for most variables, such as currently online or archived websites, annual reports, and recent social media posts. We currently do not account for the thematic evolution of CCIs over time. Additionally, CoAct now includes data on linkages to GST priorities based on an automated text analysis of publicly available sources that describe initiatives, mainly websites or documents produced by CCIs. An automated keyword search aimed to find linkages to the GST axes and key objectives as defined by the Brazilian COP30 Presidency. Most of the analysis discusses aggregate results for one or more variables through descriptive statistics; additionally, inferential statistical techniques provide insights into significant relationships between variables (at the 5% confidence level).

Sample

Our sample consists of a very diverse set of CCIs that aim to address climate change in various ways. In total, the set contains 387 CCIs, of which 186 (48%) are mainly focused on climate mitigation. A further 90 (23%) are mainly focused on adaptation, while 111 (29%) have a relatively equal focus on both adaptation and mitigation. Nature-based climate action is also prevalent in our sample, with 119 CCIs (31%) primarily addressing it. Moreover, our sample includes 181 CCIs (47%) that are listed on NAZCA, and 135 (35%) launched at recent COPs (COP26-29). Across our sample, we find differences in the emphasis placed on adaptation versus mitigation. For example, CCIs listed on NAZCA and those launched at COP29 predominantly address mitigation, while many launched at COP27 placed a greater emphasis on adaptation.

Furthermore, CCIs differ in size, as represented by the number of actors involved. The median actor count is 36 and the average is 244. However, the sample includes initiatives that engage thousands of actors at the same time, such as Race to Zero, the Global Covenant of Mayors, the SBTi and the Rainforest Alliance,

all covering more than 5000 actors. The focus on CCIs can further be distinguished based on the themes they aim to address. Table 1 shows an overview of the Marrakech Partnership themes² and the number of CCIs in our sample that address them. Overall, land use, energy, and industry are most often addressed, while water, resilience, and oceans and coastal zones are underrepresented.

Table 1: Focus on themes from the Marrakech Partnership by number of CCIs. Resilience and finance are additionally included among the themes. The categories are not mutually exclusive as CCIs can focus on more than one theme.

Theme	Number of CCIs (share)
Land use	132 (34%)
Energy	110 (28%)
Industry	99 (26%)
Human settlements	79 (20%)
Finance	65 (17%)
Transport	58 (15%)
Oceans and coastal zones	49 (13%)
Resilience	42 (11%)
Water	29 (7%)

² Recently added Marrakech Partnership theme *Inclusion* is omitted as data on the theme is not yet available.

2. Growth of Cooperative Climate Action

Key takeaway: Cooperative climate action has surged since 2013, but adaptation lags far behind mitigation.

Our sample demonstrates the increased prevalence of cooperative climate action. Figure 1 shows the number of annually launched CCIs over the last decade and the total number of active CCIs each year. Activity is defined as the period between the launch year and the year of the last recorded output. We observe a clear upward trend in active CCIs over time, although the annual number of launches fluctuates. There is a particularly high number of launches in 2015, likely connected with the emphasis on voluntary climate action around COP21. In 2019, a high number of CCIs were also launched, but the following year, the number decreased substantially. The latter is likely linked to the COVID-19 pandemic. In recent years, the number of annual launches has remained more stable, although this can partly be explained by our sample selection that aims to include CCIs launched at recent COPs. The number of adaptation CCIs or those equally focused on adaptation and mitigation lags behind mitigation CCIs. However, although mitigation CCIs are the most numerous, they are showing less growth compared to adaptation initiatives.

Figure 1: Cumulative growth and launches of CCIs in our sample. The bars represent the number of launches in the respective year, split by policy focus, while the lines represent the cumulative number of active CCIs in our sample, split by policy focus.

Increased engagement of members, participants, or signatories within individual initiatives is also an important aspect of growth. Due to limited data availability, we were only able to assess the growth of individual CCIs for a subset (129 CCIs), where we compared the size of CCIs between 2019 and 2025. Overall, we observe that most CCIs have increased in size, with over 84% showing growth. The median growth between 2019 and 2025 equals over 1.5 times the number of actors, while some CCIs have shown substantially more growth (average growth is more than tripling the number of involved actors with some individual CCIs having over a 10-fold increase).

If we further look into the themes from the Marrakech Partnership that CCIs have focused on over the last decade (see Figure 2), we see that finance is gaining traction, showing the most growth among themes between 2014 and 2024. Recent COPs have also focused on finance, potentially driving the growth of this theme among cooperative climate action. On the other hand, land use shows the least growth, although it is still the most common theme in our sample. This can partly be explained by the inclusion of many nature-focused CCIs in our sample, but it remains an important theme nonetheless. Water and transport both show limited growth and presence in the landscape, while other underrepresented themes, such as resilience and oceans and coastal zones, show more growth.

Figure 2: Growth of Marrakech Partnership themes as number of active CCIs that address the theme over time. Note: CCIs can address multiple themes at the same time, thus the total number of active CCIs is not equal to the sum of all themes.

In sum, we have seen a surge of cooperative climate action in the last decade, where both the amount of active CCIs and the size of CCIs have grown. However, growth in the number of active CCIs remains concentrated in mitigation-focused CCIs, while adaptation initiatives are still lagging. While land use is the most common theme in the sample, relevant themes for nature and adaptation, such as water and resilience, remain underrepresented.

3. Performance of Initiatives

Key takeaway 1: Output effectiveness of initiatives has increased between 2014 and 2018, after which it shows a slight decline. Output effectiveness is generally higher in initiatives with transparent and robust governance and accountability mechanisms.

Key takeaway 2: Cooperative initiatives produce mostly outputs in higher-income countries. Although adaptation efforts show slightly more outputs in lower-income countries, outputs in high-income countries remain dominant.

Output effectiveness

Effectiveness is important to consider in relation to initiatives’ promises and targets. In CoAct, we use the Function-Output-Fit (FOF) as an indicator for output effectiveness (Chan et al., 2018). This indicator assesses whether CCIs annually produce outputs that are important for the functions they aim to perform. Outputs could, for example, include published reports, organised events, or funding raised or provided. The FOF indicator measures how much of its functions each CCI addresses on an annual basis, resulting in a score between 0 (no outputs related to the CCI’s functions) and 1 (the CCI produces relevant outputs for all of its functions). Although output effectiveness, as measured by FOF scores, does not equate to actual outcomes (e.g., behaviour change among actors) or impacts (e.g., changes in environmental or social aspects), it does indicate likelihood of achieving relevant outcomes and impacts.

Output performance has shown an increasing trend between 2014 and 2018. However, after 2018, the average output performance stagnates and even slightly declines. The peak in number of launched CCIs in 2019 could contribute to the slight decrease in output performance as the higher number of CCIs can hide the effectiveness of some well-performing CCIs. We find no statistical differences in performance of mitigation or adaptation focused CCIs. We show these trends in Figure 3 as the average annual FOF for all active CCIs, as well as the shares of high to low or no output FOF scores.

Figure 3: Output performance as indicated with FOF scores. The dotted line represents the annual average FOF scores for the CCIs in our sample, while the colours indicate the share of CCIs that have a FOF score in the respective category (high: $FOF \geq 0.75$; medium high: $0.5 \leq FOF < 0.75$; medium low: $0.25 \leq FOF$

< 0.5; low FOF < 0.25). For each year, we only take active CCIs into account, meaning that the number of CCIs for each year can differ.

Accountability mechanisms can play an important role in holding CCIs responsible for acting on their targets and functions. Generally, having accountability mechanisms supports the output performance of CCIs. We have developed a continuous index that includes various aspects of accountability, such as the presence of monitoring arrangements and membership control mechanisms, but also the average number of reports published per year, and whether they have advisory or executive decision-making bodies in their governance structure. We find that output performance is strongly correlated with the accountability index. Other examples of specific CCI characteristics that are correlated with output performance can be found in Table 2.

Moreover, we also observe some variation in FOF scores based on the size of CCIs. The number of actors engaged in a CCI is positively correlated with output performance. Particularly, CCIs with less than 82 actors have lower FOF scores, while larger CCIs (more than 82 actors) have typically higher output performance. It is likely that CCIs with fewer resources have limited capacity to engage and recruit actors, while their lower capacity limits their output performance as well. The groups of CCIs in terms of actor size are based on natural breaks in the number of actors involved in CCIs.

Output performance also differs slightly between CCIs focused on specific functions. For example, CCIs focused on knowledge dissemination and campaigning are more likely to have better output performance, while CCIs focused on technical implementation, funding, and commercial product or service development have statistically lower FOF scores. However, we should be cautious when interpreting lower FOF scores in these cases as indicative of lower output performance, since some types of outputs are less frequently shared publicly by CCIs. For example, specific funding raised or provided (for funding CCIs) is less often publicly shared than research reports with the aim of disseminating knowledge.

Table 2: CCI characteristics that correlate with output performance of CCIs, including the average FOF scores for CCIs with and without the characteristic. All differences between these groups are statistically significant.

Characteristic	With	Without
Monitoring arrangements	0.456	0.362
Institutional openness	0.433	0.352
Membership control	0.436	0.372
Governance structure	0.450	0.357

Functions and outputs

CCIs can perform a wide range of functions to achieve their targets (Bernstein & Hoffmann, 2018; Hale, 2020). We include 12 functions in CoAct to map how CCIs aim to address climate change, such as setting standards and norms, creating or disseminating knowledge, or implementing climate action on the ground. CCIs in our sample generally address multiple functions. Figure 4 shows an overview of the

frequency of functions addressed by CCIs, by policy focus. We observe many CCIs that address knowledge dissemination, but we only see medium growth in active CCIs that address this function. Funding shows the most growth among active CCIs, although it still remains slightly underrepresented. Institutional capacity building and policy planning show high levels of growth and play an important role in the cooperative climate action landscape. On the other hand, training and commercial product or service development show very limited growth and are also underrepresented. We also observe some differences in the functions addressed between mitigation and adaptation CCIs. For example, standards and norms are more often addressed by mitigation-focused CCIs such as the Science-Based Targets initiative (SBTi) or the Taskforce on Climate-Related Financial Disclosures (TCFD), similar to commercial product and service development which are also more often addressed by mitigation focused CCIs such as the Global Lighting Challenge. On the other hand, funding is more often addressed by adaptation CCIs or CCIs that focus on both adaptation and mitigation.

Figure 4: Overview of functions addressed by CCIs with different policy foci. The percentages in the bars represent the share of CCIs with the respective policy focus in addressing the function. Note: CCIs can address multiple functions.

Some outputs produced by CCIs are bound to specific locations, such as event organisation, institutional tools, or funding provided to specific projects, organisations, or causes. We observe that CCIs often produce outputs in high-income contexts, with over half of all outputs, while only 7% are produced in low-

income countries³. This trend is even more strongly emphasised among mitigation-focused CCI, while adaptation CCI tend to implement more often in lower-income countries.

Governance of CCIs

Governance structures and mechanisms play an important role in how CCIs perform on aspects such as accountability, transparency, and institutional robustness. In Table 3 we provide an overview of how CCIs perform in relation to various governance-related aspects. Overall, when compared to other policy foci, mitigation CCIs have more monitoring arrangements, membership control, member commitments, and institutional openness mechanisms (in terms of clarity on how other actors might join the initiative) in place. Notably, published budgets are lacking among all CCIs.

Table 3: Overview of the share of CCIs that have governance aspects or mechanisms in place. Note: Percentages do not add up to 100%, as they show the share of CCIs in a specific group that has the governance aspect in place, without showing the share of CCIs that do not have these aspects in place.

Governance aspect	Mitigation focused	Adaptation and mitigation focused	Adaptation focused	All
Monitoring arrangements**	43.5% (81)	45.0% (50)	28.9% (26)	40.6% (157)
Membership control***	49.5% (92)	43.2% (48)	23.3% (21)	41.6% (161)
Member commitments - setting targets***	37.6% (70)	28.8% (32)	12.2% (11)	29.2% (113)
Member commitments transition plan**	29.0% (554)	26.1% (29)	13.3% (12)	24.5% (95)
Member commitments Implement and monitor***	38.7% (72)	34.2% (38)	18.9% (17)	32.8% (127)
Institutional openness***	62.9% (117)	62.2% (69)	41.1% (37)	57.6% (223)
Joint declaration	34.9% (65)	26.1% (29)	24.4% (22)	30.0% (116)
Governance structure published	41.4% (77)	53.2% (59)	42.2% (38)	45.0% (174)
Budget published	15.6% (29)	16.2% (18)	22.2% (20)	17.3% (67)
Total	186	111	90	387

Note: *** means $p < 0.01$; ** means $p < 0.05$; * means $p < 0.1$

³ Based on the World Bank Group income classifications.

4. Participatory and Implementation Patterns

Key takeaway 1: Participation has widened, but local communities and actors from lower- and lower-middle-income countries are still underrepresented.

Key takeaway 2: International NGOs and (inter-)governmental actors have strengthened their leadership roles, while domestic NGOs, businesses, and large investors show slower or declining engagement since 2020.

Key takeaway 3: The implementation of initiatives remains concentrated in high-income countries of the Global North. Although implementation in Global South contexts is increasing, significant gaps persist.

Our database distinguishes actors by type, i.e., businesses and industry, investors, education and research organizations, non-for profits and non-governmental organizations operating internationally (INGOs) or domestically (DNGOs), indigenous peoples and local communities (IPLCs), as well as (sub-)national governments and international organizations (IOs). Among the actors that are part of CCIs, we distinguish among funders (providing financial support), leaders (leading and coordinating), and/or participants (including partners, members, and signatories). Figure 5 shows the distribution of actor types across these three roles.

The main funders of initiatives are national governments (27%), INGOs (23%), businesses (18%), and IOs (13%). Similarly, over 60% of all leading actors in CCIs are IOs, INGOs, or national governments. Almost 50% of all initiatives include either an INGO or an IO as lead partner. Looking at all the instances of participation (91,867), we find a dominance of business (45%) and subnational actors (30%). This distribution is influenced by the presence of large city and business networks in the sample, such as the Global Covenant of Mayors, Race to Zero and the SBTi. In contrast, DNGOs, as well as IPLCs, are underrepresented across all three groups. Only five initiatives in our sample include IPLCs as leaders and eight as participants, which can have important implications for justice and equity in decision-making processes.

Figure 5: Shares of funders, leaders, and participants by actor type. The values reflect the distribution of actors by role across all CCI. An initiative can have multiple leaders, funders, and/or participants.

The regional⁴ and income-level distribution of actor types shows a strong concentration of activity in high-income contexts (Table 4). Europe and Northern America dominate across all roles, accounting for more than 80% of funders and over 70% of leaders. Over 90% of funders and 80% of leaders are located in high-income countries (HIC), indicating that financial and organizational control is heavily skewed towards wealthier economies. Participation is more geographically diverse, with higher shares from Asia (17%) and Latin America and the Caribbean (9%), although Europe still accounts for over half of all participants (55%). Lower-middle-income (LMC) and low-income countries (LIC) together represent only about 11% of participants, 10% of leaders and 4% of funders, highlighting a persistent imbalance in engagement and influence.

⁴ All country classifications in this report are based on the UNSD regional classifications (M49 Standard). Income groups are based on The World Bank Group's classifications for 2024.

Table 4: Distribution of funders, leaders and participants by region and income group (in %). LAC = Latin America and the Caribbean, HIC = High-income countries, UMC = Upper middle-income countries, LMC = Lower middle-income countries, LIC = Lower-income countries.

Region	Income Group									
	Africa	Asia	Europe	LAC	Northern America	Oceania	HIC	UMC	LMC	LIC
Funders	2.25	8.04	50.59	2.75	34.22	2.16	91.57	4.41	3.92	0.1
Leaders	7.96	10.47	45.26	8.07	25.52	2.73	80.26	9.38	8.83	1.53
Participants	6.34	16.78	55.16	9.15	10.22	2.35	74.88	13.78	9.62	1.72

There are notable differences in the composition of actor types across initiatives with distinct policy foci. Among CCIs primarily targeting mitigation, business actors account for 66% of participants and 22% of funders, following national governments as main funding actors (27%). Leadership in mitigation-focused initiatives is concentrated among IOs (23%) and INGOs (21%), reflecting their continued prominence in coordinating global mitigation efforts. By contrast, adaptation-focused CCIs show a stronger presence of public and international actors. National governments represent 28% of participants, while INGOs and businesses each account for around 15%. National governments (28%) and INGOs (24%) are the main funders, whereas leadership is concentrated among IOs (31%) and INGOs (24%). CCIs that balance mitigation and adaptation exhibit a different dynamic, with subnational actors playing a central role, comprising 56% of participants and taking on a larger share of leadership (7%) than in other categories. Research institutions also feature more prominently as leaders in equally focused initiatives (10%), while INGOs emerge as the most frequent leaders (21%) and funders (29%). Overall, these patterns show that mitigation-oriented initiatives heavily rely on business participation but remain institutionally led by international and transnational actors. In contrast, adaptation efforts are anchored in intergovernmental leadership, while initiatives addressing both goals foster more diverse and multi-level governance engagement. It is important to note that these results reflect the overall number of participation, leadership, and funding instances across all CCIs and are therefore influenced by differences in initiative size. Larger CCIs, predominantly networks of businesses and subnational actors mentioned above, tend to increase the relative share of these actors in the aggregate counts. However, the overall trends remain largely consistent when excluding large actor initiatives⁵. The main deviation appears among dual-focused initiatives, where national governments (29%) become the most frequent participants once large city networks are filtered out.

Since 2013, the evolution of leadership across key actor groups has been uneven. INGOs and international organizations experienced the most notable expansion, with both showing sharp increases in engagement around 2019 followed by continued, though more moderate, growth in subsequent years. By 2024, we observed the highest number of leadership instances in active CCIs among INGOs and international organizations, with 216 and 240 instances respectively. National governments recorded a major rise in 2015, before entering a period of slower but steady expansion. Subnational governments expanded their engagement particularly in 2016, but have since shown unsteady and more moderate growth. By contrast,

⁵ Large actor initiatives are defined based on initiatives with more than 243 participants, which is based on natural breaks in the data.

domestic NGOs, while starting from a low base, gradually increased their leadership presence until 2019, after which engagement has largely plateaued. Leadership instances by businesses and large investors expanded significantly in 2015, but show a declining trend among active CCIs in recent years. Figure 6 illustrates this development for selected actor types.

Overall, we observe a differentiated pattern of leadership development. Importantly, we find peaks in 2015 and 2019 marking periods of cross-sector mobilization. However, while intergovernmental and governmental actors continue to consolidate their leadership roles, domestic NGOs, business actors, and large investors show slower growth or even declining engagement as leaders of initiatives over the past five years. Notably, international NGOs have emerged as a major and sustained civil society force (see also Green, 2024).

Figure 6: Leadership development of selected actor types, 2013-2024. The figure shows the development of leadership over time for actors belonging to international organizations (top left), business and industry (bottom left), as well as international (top right) and domestic non-profits & NGOs (bottom right). The bars indicate instances of leadership by launch year of initiatives, while the line shows the cumulative total of leadership instances among all initiatives active in a given year.

When examining actor patterns, it is also relevant to note that many participants assume responsibility for setting targets, drafting action plans, and/or monitoring progress upon joining an initiative. Such commitments most often target businesses, investors, and subnational governments, which together account for more than 81% of the total participation instances. Figure 7 shows how the proportion of participants who are subject to membership control mechanisms varies across actor types. We note that only 2.8% of all subnational participation instances are not linked to any type of climate commitment

through a CCI. In contrast, larger shares of business (28%) and investor participation (40%) are not associated with any kind of climate commitment. The large proportion of participants subject to membership control among certain actor types appears to be linked to a few initiatives that require very large memberships to establish targets, draft plans, and monitor progress. For instance, the Global Covenant of Mayors (GCOM) registers over 13 thousand instances of subnational governments that are required to comply with all three types of commitments. Similarly, the Race to Zero and the Science Based Targets Initiative set requirements for more than 14,600 and 8,900 participating actors.

Figure 7: Share of actor types subject to membership control mechanisms. Percentages do not add to 100% because some instances of participation are linked to one or more commitment types.

The distribution of actor types targeted by CCIs varies across policy foci but reveals consistent patterns (Figure 8). Business actors as well as national and subnational governments are the most frequent targets overall, reflecting their central roles in both implementing and enabling climate action. Business actors are particularly prominent as targets of mitigation-focused initiatives, followed by national and subnational governments and investors; this highlights their potential to reduce emissions (either directly or through targeted policies) and mobilize finance. In adaptation-focused initiatives, national governments are the primary targets, followed by subnational governments and businesses. In contrast, the general public is seldom directly addressed, especially within adaptation-focused CCIs. IPLCs are targeted by 21% of initiatives, indicating a limited inclusion of locally grounded stakeholders again. However, their share is higher (around 30%) when looking at the subset of both adaptation and dual-focus initiatives.

Figure 8: Target actors of CCI by actor type and policy focus (%). The figure depicts the share of initiatives targeting each actor type, split by main policy focus (mitigation, adaptation, or both). Note that each initiative can target multiple actors simultaneously.

To further provide insights into questions of inclusive decision-making in CCIs, we analysed the presence of organizational structures. Nearly 70% of initiatives report a dedicated secretariat or staff, while little over a third (36.7%) and a fourth (26.4%) report having either an executive decision-making body (e.g., a steering committee) or an advisory body. Figure 9 provides an overview of the composition of these governance structures, including the types of actors they involve when present in the organizational structure of CCIs. We then compared the composition of these bodies with expected distributions based on the target actors that CCIs aim to influence or engage, thereby providing evidence on whether actors targeted by initiatives are potentially included in decision-making. Chi-squared tests of independence at a 90% confidence level between observed and expected distributions indicate that subnational governments and DNGOs are significantly underrepresented in both executive decision-making bodies and advisory bodies, even when CCIs aim to engage or change the behaviour of these actor types. Similarly, IPLCs are the most significantly underrepresented actor type in executive decision-making bodies, highlighting gaps in equitable representation. Conversely, IOs and INGOs have significant roles in these organizational structures, indicating their potential influence on the decision-making and governance processes within initiatives.

Figure 9: Composition of organizational governance structures of CCIs. The figure illustrates the percentage of initiatives in which a particular actor type is represented in a specific governance structure. Percentages are calculated against total initiatives that report having said structure.

Equity and justice concerns can be further evaluated by questioning who stands to benefit from the activities of CCIs. The analysis draws on CoAct data for planned and ongoing geographies of implementation. In this regard, approximately 85% of the CCIs in the sample report one or more countries or territories for planned or ongoing implementation, totalling 8,623 instances (Figure 10 presents a map with their geographic distribution). Europe ranks first with 27% total instances. Africa, Asia, and Latin America and the Caribbean follow with 25%, 22% and 17% respectively. The least number of instances are registered in Oceania (5.1%) and Northern America (3.5%). Based on income, most implementation instances occur in high-income countries (42%), followed by lower-middle-income (25%) and upper-middle-income (24%) countries; the remaining instances are registered in low-income countries (10%). These trends showcase that implementation is mainly focused on Global North contexts, as evidenced also by the high share of implementation instances in G20 (38%), OECD (36%) and EU (20%) countries.

When considering the policy focus of CCIs, nearly half of the implementation instances are focused on climate mitigation (49%), one-third on equally focused efforts (33%), and the rest on adaptation (18%). Commensurate with the principle of *common but differentiated responsibilities*, we could expect that more mitigation will be Global North-based, whereas more adaptation action should be expected in the Global South. Indeed, implementation efforts in OECD, G20, and European Union countries are predominantly focused on mitigation. In the Global South—particularly in lower to low-middle income regions and countries—initiatives tend to prioritize adaptation. For countries with high vulnerability to climate change, namely Landlocked Developing Countries (LLDC), Least Developed Countries (LDC), and Small Island Developing States (SIDS) implementation often focuses on adaptation or equally focused initiatives, which is considered a priority in these regions. Notably, the latter trend is also predominant in

Sub-Saharan Africa, indicating potential positive outcomes in a region likely to experience some of the most adverse impacts of climate change.

Figure 10: Instances of implementation by country or territory. The map showcases the number of initiatives reporting planned or ongoing implementation in a specific country or territory.

Analysing patterns of implementation and potential benefits from cooperative action must also consider factors such as population size or emissions intensity in specific geographical contexts to provide more nuanced conclusions. Hence, we identified over- and under-represented regions per policy focus, aligning with expected distributions based on total population estimates. This approach shows that implementation of all types of CCIs is predominant in the EU, as well as in OECD, G20, and high-income country groups, further indicating that most cooperative climate action is still biased towards implementation in Global North contexts. However, when accounting for particular vulnerability characteristics and considering their total population, significant implementation is observed in SIDS, LDCs, and LLDCs. Regarding overall implementation in Global South contexts, we note the significant implementation of adaptation and equally focused initiatives in low-income countries. However, we note that all types of initiatives show under-implementation (as expected by the total population) in middle-income countries.

Overall, while CCIs embody the principle of shared responsibility in global climate governance, their current composition remains concentrated among well-resourced institutions and countries. Enhancing inclusiveness will require stronger mechanisms for equitable participation and leadership, particularly for actors from low- and middle-income countries, local governments, and community-based organizations, to ensure that cooperative action more fully reflects diverse needs, contexts, and capacities.

5. Looking Ahead: Contributions to GST Priorities

Key Takeaway: Initiatives often address multiple thematic axes and create synergies that should be leveraged, in line with the integrated approach promoted by the GST and the COP30 Action Agenda. As priorities evolve over time and across regions, it is crucial to maintain appropriately balanced attention across all thematic areas.

The GST is guiding action towards the Paris Agreement goals (Aranha Correa do Lago 2025). The COP30 Action Agenda, inspired by the GST, calls on all stakeholders - governments, civil society, businesses, and local communities - to join a collective “mutirão” for climate action. The Agenda aims to turn climate action from “a cacophony into an orchestrated symphony” (cf. Peterson, 2025), organised around six thematic GST axes, further split up into 30 key objectives:

Figure 11: Thematic GST axes, territory and key objectives. Axes and key objectives as defined by the Brazilian COP30 presidency.

We use automated text analysis on a corpus of text related to the 387 initiatives in our sample to link them to GST axes and show how priorities are distributed over time and space, allowing us to highlight how CCIs have contributed to these thematic areas, and what they can do going forward.

Table 5 gives an overview over key variables along each axis, demonstrating what thematic areas initiatives are focusing on, where synergies exist, and how initiatives with different thematic foci might differ in their behaviour. There are no significant differences in performance (average FOF score). Transparency across axes does not vary in statistically significant ways either, even if initiatives that address axes 2 (Stewarding Forests, Oceans and Biodiversity) and 3 (Transforming Agriculture and Food Systems) publish budgets or governance structures or have monitoring arrangements at slightly higher rates.

Table 5: Overview of key variables by axis. KO = Key Objective, FOF = Function-Output Fit

Axis	1 - Energy, Industry, Transport	2 - Forests, Oceans, Biodiversity	3 - Agriculture & Food Systems	4 - Cities, Infrastructure, Water	5- Human & Social Development	6 - Cross-Cutting
Prevalence (%)	46	38.5	35.3	37.7	49.7	80.7
Most prevalent Key Objective	4	6	8	15	18	28
Top 3 Axis overlaps	6: 84.9% 5: 54.1% 4: 45.3%	6: 84.7% 3: 61.8% 5: 59.0%	6: 83.3% 2: 67.4% 5: 61.4%	6: 87.9% 5: 61.7% 1: 55.3%	6: 85.5% 1: 50.0% 4: 46.8%	5: 52.6% 1: 48.3% 4: 41.1%
Published governance structure (%)	45.3	52.1	47.7	46.1	45.2	47.4
Monitoring arrangement (%)	38.6	40.6	43.2	41.4	38.4	41.5
Published budget (%)	14.8	22.7	23.7	15.9	20.5	19.7
Average FOF score	0.403	0.405	0.405	0.397	0.409	0.405

Not all axes appear equally according to the mapping. For Axis 6 (Unleashing Enablers and Accelerators), as a broad, cross-cutting axis, this is hardly surprising. However, nearly half of all initiatives also refer to Axis 5 (Fostering Human and Social Development). This is largely driven by Axis 5 carrying some cross-cutting functions, especially through its focus on capacity building, represented by its most often referred to key objective 18, focused on “education, capacity-building and job creation”.

Initiatives can promote synergies by contributing to multiple axes, notably between 1 and 4, and 2 and 3. Stewarding forests, oceans, and biodiversity (axis 3) supports sustainable agriculture and food systems (axis 2), while transforming food systems reduces pressure on natural habitats. Many initiatives already address these interdependencies—for example, the FABLE Consortium develops national food and land-use pathways aligned with global sustainability goals, balancing agricultural productivity, biodiversity conservation, and climate mitigation. Similarly, efforts to expand renewable energy (axis 1) are often paired with circular economy or pollution reduction action (axis 4), as seen in the Transformative Urban Mobility Initiative (TUMI), which improves urban transport and air quality while mitigating carbon emissions. Underrepresented overlaps, such as energy–nature, food–energy, and cities–ecosystems, present urgent opportunities. Nature-focused initiatives like the Global Campaign for Nature and the Global Forest Coalition illustrate potential trade-offs when mitigation intersects with lands and waters managed by IPLCs, while initiatives like the Ocean Risk and Resilience Action Alliance (ORRAA) demonstrate integrated solutions, combining ocean conservation, renewable energy, and circular economy approaches to deliver climate, biodiversity, and human well-being co-benefits.

GST axes over time: active initiatives and launches

Comparing initiative launches and activity across axes over the last decade reveals distinct patterns (see Figure 12). Over the last ten years, thematic axes have shifted, with noticeable peaks in launches for each axis. Axis 1 (Energy, Industry and Transport) had a comparably lower number of active initiatives early on, but attention - for example during peak launch years in 2021 and 2024 - seems to have consistently increased, with it now being the axis with the most active initiatives. Similarly, but at a lower level, Axis 2 (Stewarding Forests, Oceans and Biodiversity) saw relatively low numbers of launches before 2019 but has since stabilised at a higher prevalence. Axis 3 (Transforming Agriculture and Food Systems) had the highest relative number of launches in 2015 but has since somewhat levelled off in comparison to the other axes. Axis 4 had relatively few active initiatives early on, but has seen an increase in recent years, with a peak in launches in 2022. Shifts in initiative launches and active initiatives across axes suggest changing priorities and overall public attention. For example, the relative launch peaks in 2018 and 2022 for Axis 4, which partly focus on urban contexts, coincide with peaks in scientific publications on urban climate change during the same years (Sekyere et al. 2025). Overall, these patterns highlight the importance of maintaining appropriately balanced support across axes, even if priorities shift over time.

Figure 12: Active initiatives (lines) and new launches (bars) by Axes 2014-2024. Note that each initiative can contribute to multiple Axes simultaneously. Cross-cutting Axis 6 is excluded from this graph. We do not account for thematic priorities changing within initiatives over time.

GST axis focus by geography of implementation

Thematic priorities are distributed unevenly across regions. Figure 12 compares the geographic distribution of regions of implementation across Axis 1 (Energy, Industry, and Transport) and Axis 2 (Forests, Oceans, and Biodiversity), which show the most contrasting spatial patterns. Axis 2, but also Axis 3 (Agriculture and Food Systems), are more prevalent in initiatives targeting low-income countries, while

Axis 1 dominates in initiatives focused on high-income countries. Axis 4 (Cities, Infrastructure, and Water) is comparatively underrepresented in low-income countries.

Figure 13: Difference between number of initiatives addressing Axis 1 and Axis 2 by country. Blue signifies a majority for Axis 1, red a majority for Axis 2. Note that each initiative can contribute to multiple Axes simultaneously.

This distribution is not necessarily problematic and aligns with intuitive expectations: initiatives in lower-income countries tend to prioritize agriculture, biodiversity, supporting livelihoods that are more closely tied to ecosystems and biodiversity, also protecting some of the most important biodiversity hotspots - such as Indonesia, or the Democratic Republic of Congo (Neugarten et al. 2024). In higher-income countries, the focus shifts toward energy transitions, and urban infrastructure, reflecting both the mitigation potential and the capacity to implement technologically intensive solutions. Overall, the heatmap underscores that global initiatives seem to be tailored to regional contexts, balancing development priorities with climate mitigation and adaptation strategies.

6. Recommendations for the Next Five Years

Over the past decade, cooperative climate initiatives (CCIs) have played a crucial role in mobilizing diverse actors and accelerating climate action across sectors and regions. Yet, persistent imbalances and capacity gaps limit their overall impact. The following recommendations outline key priorities for orchestrators, COP Presidencies, and CCIs themselves to strengthen coherence, inclusiveness, and effectiveness over the next five years—ensuring that cooperative climate action continues to evolve in line with global goals and emerging needs.

Orchestrators, COP Presidencies, and CCIs could play a role in further emphasizing adaptation as an important climate aspect and continuing the increasing focus on resilience. Our analysis demonstrates that some thematic areas remain underrepresented, individual initiatives and orchestrators could emphasize these themes in cooperative climate action, while COP Presidencies can include these themes more explicitly in their agenda-setting. Particularly, adaptation and nature-related themes such as water, oceans & coastal zones, and resilience are underrepresented, although the latter two have shown increased emphasis over time.

One way to structure orchestration to balance these different themes is by aligning actions with thematic axes inspired by the Global Stocktake (GST), as proposed by the Brazilian COP30 presidency. Over the past ten years, CCIs have already shown broad awareness of the topics related to the different thematic axes, as well as the synergies connecting them. Policymakers and orchestrators should further strengthen alignment with the GST and the Action Agenda through balanced support, and the promotion of integrated, cross-axis action. They should support existing synergies, for example between action targeting nature and food systems, but also explore and acknowledge less commonly addressed synergies and trade-offs, for example between energy–nature, food–energy, and cities–ecosystems.

Output effectiveness of CCIs should also be improved by supporting capacity and accountability mechanisms, as we observed a decreasing trend in output effectiveness since 2018. Smaller CCIs show lower output effectiveness, likely due to limited capacities. We urge orchestrators and powerful actors to support the capacity of these CCIs. Moreover, accountability mechanisms generally support output effectiveness, which is confirmed by strong correlations between accountability mechanisms and output performance. The majority of CCIs still have no monitoring arrangements, membership control mechanisms, published budgets, or transparent governance structures; these elements could play a role in supporting both accountability and effectiveness. However, accountability should also be improved beyond transparency and individual CCIs. For example, targets set by initiatives should be made more comparable, and best practice guidance or accountability standards for CCIs could play a role if emphasized sufficiently. The enhancement of accountability mechanisms is already partially being addressed by ongoing processes stemming from the UN High Level Expert Group (HLEG) workstream on integrity and the Net Zero Emissions Commitments of Non-Party Stakeholders, the Net Zero Data Public Utility, as well as the ongoing redevelopment of NAZCA. These processes should also consider the vital role that capacities and accountability mechanisms play in improving the effectiveness of CCI output performance.

Strengthening cooperative climate action requires greater inclusiveness and sustained engagement of non-state and subnational actors. Indigenous peoples and local communities remain underrepresented in CCIs, particularly in leadership roles and governance structures related to decision-making, such as steering committees or advisory bodies. Strengthening their inclusion should be a priority to ensure that cooperative action reflects diverse local perspectives and knowledge systems. At the same time, it is essential to sustain and reinvigorate the engagement of businesses, investors, and local civil society organizations in leadership positions. Recent patterns show a stagnation in their involvement, possibly driven by geopolitical and economic uncertainty, growing climate change denialism, and political polarization. Continued mobilization of non-state leadership across all types of actors can help maintain momentum and drive ambitious collaborative climate action.

Orchestrators, COP Presidencies, and CCIs should work to correct persistent geographic imbalances in implementation, which remains concentrated in high-income contexts. Although adaptation-related implementation is occurring in vulnerable countries, middle- and low-income countries are still underrepresented. Prioritizing implementation and location-based outputs in these regions—such as events, investments, and capacity-building efforts—should go hand in hand with increasing the participation of local actors. Strengthening their involvement would not only enhance effectiveness but also advance procedural justice and ensure that cooperative climate action reflects diverse regional needs and perspectives.

7. Conclusion

Our mapping of the landscape of cooperative climate action over the last decade provides us with important lessons. First, we show that cooperative climate action, as represented by the activities of CCIs, has grown substantially over the last 10 years, both in the number of active initiatives and their size. Focus on adaptation has grown rapidly over the years, but it still lags behind cooperative mitigation efforts. Particularly, finance-themed initiatives have gained traction, while other aspects of climate change have remained dominant in the landscape. Land use, energy, and industry remain important themes, and knowledge dissemination, institutional capacity building, and policy planning are common functions of initiatives. Moreover, CCIs frequently span multiple thematic areas and generate synergies that should be harnessed, consistent with the integrated approach advocated by the COP30 Action Agenda, inspired by the Global Stocktake. As priorities shift over time and vary by region, it is essential to ensure a well-balanced focus across all thematic areas.

Moreover, we show that output performance initially grew rapidly between 2014 and 2018, after which it showed a slight decline. For smaller, less resourceful CCIs or when accountability mechanisms are lacking, output effectiveness is lower, stressing the importance of capacity and accountability. Furthermore, location-based outputs are mainly produced in high-income contexts, showing little change over the last decade. Although adaptation outputs are slightly more often produced in lower-income countries, persistent gaps remain.

Although many types of non-state and subnational actors are involved in CCIs, overall we observe that international organisations and governmental actors continue to consolidate their leadership roles, while domestic NGOs, business actors and large investors show slower growth. International NGOs have emerged as a major and sustained civil society force that steers CCIs.

The current landscape provides us with additional insights that are difficult to capture over time.

Participation in CCIs is dominated by businesses and subnational governments, for instance through large corporate initiatives or city networks. On the other hand, international NGOs, international organisations and national governments play a more important role in leading and funding CCIs. Justice and equity gaps also persist. Indigenous peoples and local communities are missing in CCIs in relevant decision-making positions. Business actors are especially common in mitigation-focused CCIs, while adaptation CCIs tend to leverage public and international actors. Moreover, European and Northern American actors dominate the CCI landscape, while actors from low, lower-middle, and upper-middle income countries are generally more limited in involvement in CCIs. Similar trends in implementation patterns show that most initiatives focus on Global North contexts. However, there are positive developments. For instance, adaptation actions are increasingly being implemented in highly vulnerable contexts, with planned or ongoing activities particularly in SIDS, LDCs, LLDCs, low-income countries, and Sub-Saharan Africa.

About This Analysis. This study is based on preliminary data. Further validation, including blind double-coding and temporal analysis of CCIs, is ongoing. Updated data and extended analyses—covering the

thematic evolution of initiatives and linkages to GST priorities—will be made available by the authors in subsequent releases.

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